

indicating a certain degree of GLH adaptation to the variety. Although Ptb

8 and IR42 have the same major gene for GLH resistance, the rate of

adaptation was faster on Ptb 8 than on IR42. *S*

Reaction of rices to *Sogatella furcifera* in free-choice and no-choice seedling bulk tests

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We evaluated the reactions of N22, ARC10239, ADR52, Podiwi A8, N'Diang Marie, and IR2035-117-3 to *S. furcifera* in the IRRI greenhouse in 1984. TN1 was the susceptible check.

In the free-choice test, seeds were sown in 60- × 40- × 10-cm wooden seedboxes. One row of 25 seeds per entry was sown for each of 3 replications. Seven-day-old seedlings were infested with five 2d- and 3d-instar *S. furcifera* nymphs per seedling. Damage was rated at 8 d when susceptible TN1 died and 10 d when most varieties showed hopperburn.

Reaction of rice varieties to *S. furcifera* in free-choice and no-choice tests, IRRI, 1984.

Variety	Damage rating ^a		
	Free-choice test		No-choice test
	8	10	
N22	5 (0.00) b	7 (0.57) ab	4 (-0.28) bc
ARC10239	4 (-0.38) ab	6 (0.31) a	5 (-0.05) c
ADR52	3 (-0.57) ab	3 (-0.57) a	3 (-0.46) b
Podiwi A8	4 (-0.19) b	6 (0.50) ab	7 (0.45) d
N'Diang Marie	5 (0.00) b	6 (0.38) ab	4 (-0.17) bc
IR2035-117-3	2 (-0.88) a	4 (-0.19) a	1 (-1.38) a
TN1	9 (1.49) c	9 (1.49) b	9 (1.27) e

^a Test for paired values for no-choice and free-choice at P = 0.05 = nonsignificant. Figures in parentheses are transformed score values for ranked data.

Reaction was rated by the *Standard evaluation system for rice* 0 to 9 scale (see table).

In the no-choice test, 19-d-old potted plants were covered with a 10- × 90-cm mylar cage and arranged in randomized complete block design with 5 replications. Five pair of 3-d-old *S. furcifera*

adults were released per cage. Damage was rated 21 d later (see table).

IR2035-117-3 was most resistant in both tests. At 10 d after infestation in the free-choice test, ADR52 performed as well as IR2035-117-3. TN1 was most susceptible, followed by Podiwi A8 and N22. *S*

Response of resistant rices to brown planthoppers (BPH) collected in Mindanao, Philippines

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IR36 and IR42 (with *bph 2* gene for resistance to BPH *Nilaparvata lugens*) have been extensively grown in the Philippines, Indonesia, and Vietnam for about 7 yr. In 1982, they were attacked by BPH in Mindanao, Philippines. A BPH population was collected in Mindanao and evaluated at IRRI using the standard seedbox screening, population growth development, and growth index studies. IR26 with *Bph 1*, IR36 and IR42 with *bph 2*, and Rathu Heenati and IR56 with *Bph 3* were screened for resistance.

In the population development study, 10 newly hatched nymphs were caged on 35-d-old potted test varieties. The number of BPH/cage was recorded 40 d

1. Resistance of selected varieties to Mindanao BPH, 1983.

2. Resistance of selected varieties to Mindanao BPH, 1984. M-36, M-25, and M-42 = Mindanao BPH reared on IR36, IR26, and IR42, respectively.